

Notes

Chemical examination of the flowers of *Saraca indica*

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SARACA indica (N.O. Leguminosae). *Uses*—Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—Several workers have investigated other parts²⁻⁶. *Present work*—Air dried flowers were successively extracted with hot petroleum ether, ethylacetate and 95% alcohol. A yellow deposit obtained in all the three extracts was filtered.

The yellow deposit on chromatography over neutral alumina followed by preparative T.L.C. yielded compound A which was identified as β -sitosterol.

The ethylacetate and alcoholic extracts on column chromatography over silica gel afforded compounds B, C, D and E. Compound B was found to be identical with quercetin⁷. Compounds C, D and E were flavone glycosides and were identified as Kaempferol-3-O- β -D-glucoside⁸, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucoside⁹ and apigenin-7-O- β -D-glucoside¹⁰ respectively from a study of u.v. spectral data, identical m.p., m.m.p. and degradations.

Tanins, catechins and leucoyanins were also found in its alcoholic extract and were not studied in detail.

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Chemical examination of the flowers of *Grewia-asiatica* Linn.

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GREWIA asiatica Linn. (N.O. Tiliaceae). *Uses*: Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—On stem cuttings², seed oil³ and stem bark⁴. *Present work*—Air dried flowers were extracted with hot alcohol, filtered and kept for few days. A yellow deposit was obtained, filtered and the concentrated filtrate was extracted successively with petroleum ether, ethylacetate, acetone and ethanol. The yellow deposit was also fractionated into petroleum ether, ethylacetate soluble fractions and mixed with petroleum ether and ethylacetate extracts obtained as above. The petroleum ether extract on column chromatography over neutral alumina afforded compounds A, D, E and F. The ethylacetate extract on column chromatography on silica gel yielded compounds B, C, G and H.

Compound A was identified as β -sitosterol⁵ (m.p., m.m.p., superimposable IR) and compound B was found to be identical with quercetin⁶. Compound C, C₂₂H₂₂O₁₁, m.p. 294°-6° and compound G, C₂₁H₂₂O₁₀, m.p. 225°-6° was identified as quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucoside⁷ and Naringenin-7-O- β -D-glucoside⁸ respectively from the studies of their u.v. spectral data, degradations, m.p. and mixed m.p. The compound H, m.p. 248°-51° was characterized as Naringenin⁸. Besides these four amino acids namely proline, lysine, glutaric acid and phenyl alanine and three free sugars, namely, glucose, xylose and arabinose were identified by paper Co-chromatography with authentic samples in acetone and ethanol extracts. Work on other compounds is in progress.

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